

Adsorption Behaviour of Anionic Dyes on Guar gum Derivatives: Reclamation of Textile Effluent

R. C. KAPOOR, ADITYA PRAKASH and S. L. KALANI

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

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The adsorption behaviour of some anionic dyes used in textile industries on newer synthesised adsorbents from guar gum, namely quaternary aminised $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}^+]$, $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}^+]$, diethyl amino hydroxy propyl and cross-linked derivatives have been studied. Trimethyl aminised $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}^+]$ derivative was found to be a better adsorbent for the removal of color of textile effluent in both alkaline and acidic conditions. However, the most effective pH range was from 3 to 5. The treated effluent can be reused in the textile industry.

MANY industries in India presently discharge untreated water on land or in natural streams causing pollution of surface water, ground water and land. As a result of rapid industrialisation the water resources development schemes and water distribution systems are unable to keep pace with its increased demand. The reclamation of water for industrial reuse would minimise both these problems.

In view of the high cost and tedious procedure for the regeneration of activated carbon, there is a continuing search for low cost efficient adsorbents¹⁻⁵. Recently we have reported the synthesis of some guar gum derivatives and their applicability in the removal of colour and toxic constituents from textile waste water⁶. We, herewith, report the adsorption and desorption characteristics of some reactive, hydrolysed reactive and direct dyes on the synthesised derivatives. Such dyes are the major constituents of the colouring matter of effluents of local textile industries.

Experimental

Adsorbents: The adsorbents used in this study, namely quaternary aminised $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}^+]$, $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}^+]$, diethylaminohydroxypropyl and cross-linked guar were synthesised as described earlier⁶.

Dyes: The following six dyes (Atul Products, India) were selected for these studies and were used as such: Procion Orange H₂R, Procion Brill Blue H₂G, Direct Red, Direct Helio-B, Procion Red M₂B (hydrolysed), Procion Blue MR (hydrolysed). The solutions of dyes were prepared freshly in distilled water. Weighted quantities of guar derivatives were contacted with aqueous solution of dyes (100 ppm, 20 ml). The system was equilibrated for 60 min at ambient temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ$) with constant stirring. The initial pH of the dye solutions were adjusted by adding requisite quantities of dilute hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide

solutions. The equilibrated dye solutions were centrifuged for 20 min at 10,000 rpm in a T24 model (GDR) centrifuge. The supernatant solutions were analysed colorimetrically for residual dye concentrations at the maximum absorbance region of each dye using AIMIL MK II spectrophotometer.

Textile industrial waste water: Samples were collected from two main open drains in Jodhpur industrial area. The water was highly coloured (brownish purple), alkaline (pH 9.4-11.3) and foul smelling. Its detailed characteristics have been reported elsewhere⁷. The samples were allowed to stand for 4 h, the supernatant liquid decanted and pH adjusted to the desired level with hydrochloric acid. Different amounts of quaternary aminised $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}^+]$ guar derivatives were contacted with 100 ml effluent for 24 h with periodic shaking. The effluent was then centrifuged and O.D. of the supernatant liquid was measured.

Results and Discussion

The data regarding adsorption of reactive (procion orange H₂R and procion brill blue H₂G), direct (direct red and direct helio B) and hydrolysed reactive (procion red M₂B and procion brill blue MR) dyes from their aqueous solutions after treatment with different amounts of quaternary aminised guar $[(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{N}^+]$ derivative at pH 7 were plotted according to Freundlich equation;

$$X/m = KC^n$$

where (X/m) stands for the amount of solute (dye) per unit weight of adsorbent and C for equilibrium concentration of the dye in solution while K and n are constants. The plots of log X/m against log C in each case (Fig. 1) yielded straight lines from whose slopes and intercepts the

Fig. 1. $\log \frac{x}{m}$ vs $\log C$ plot at pH 7 : —■—■—■— Direct helio B, —▲—▲—▲— Procion red M_6B (hydrolysed), —●—●—●— Procion orange H_6R , —□—□—□— Procion blue MR (hydrolysed), —△—△—△— Direct red, —○—○—○— Procion brill blue H_6G .

TABLE 1—ADSORPTION CAPACITY (K) AND INTENSITY OF ADSORPTION $1/n$ OF QUATERNARY AMINISED $[(CH_3)_3N^+]$ GUAR DERIVATIVE CONTACTED WITH DIFFERENT ANIONIC DYES AT pH 7

Sl. no.	Dye used	Adsorption capacity $K \times 10^3$		Intensity of adsorption $1/n$	
		Graphical	Calcd.	Graphical	Calcd.
1.	Procion brill blue H_6G	3.16	3.21	0.52	0.51
2.	Procion orange H_6R	7.94	7.32	0.25	0.15
3.	Direct helio-B	1.70	1.07	0.50	0.62
4.	Direct red	5.62	5.54	0.46	0.46
5.	Procion red M_6B (hydrolysed)	6.60	6.44	0.16	0.16
6.	Procion blue MR (hydrolysed)	4.67	4.63	0.44	0.43

values of $1/n$ and K were obtained. The values calculated by least square method were in good agreement with the observed values (Table 1).

Influence of pH: The effect of pH on the adsorption was studied on the direct helio B dye using quaternary aminised guar $[(CH_3)_3N^+]$ derivative as the adsorbent. The values of K and $1/n$ at pH 3, 5, 7 and 10 were calculated and are given in Table 2. From these values it is apparent that the adsorption of dye increases with decrease in pH.

TABLE 2—ADSORPTION CAPACITY (K) AND INTENSITY OF ADSORPTION $1/n$ OF QUATERNARY AMINISED $[(CH_3)_3N^+]$ GUAR DERIVATIVE CONTACTED WITH HELIO-B AT DIFFERENT pH

Sl. no.	pH	Adsorption capacity $K \times 10^3$		Intensity of adsorption $1/n$	
		Graphical	Calcd.	Graphical	Calcd.
1.	3	3.09	2.94	0.42	0.44
2.	5	2.09	2.13	0.47	0.48
3.	7	1.70	1.08	0.50	0.62
4.	10	1.35	1.36	0.54	0.54

The mechanism of adsorption may be considered as a mixed effect of the classical and chromato-

graphic adsorption. The improved adsorption at lower pH may be explained on the assumption that the adsorbent is anionic in nature due to the presence of hydroxyl groups of guar. Further, some negative sites are also introduced as galactomannans are susceptible to air oxidation in alkaline medium leading to the generation of acidic end groups⁸. These and other anionic groups are neutralised by protonation at low pH, which facilitates the diffusion of dye molecules in the vicinity of the adsorbent.

The reduced adsorption at higher pH can be due to the abundance of OH^- and consequent ionic repulsion between the surface partial negative charge on the adsorbent and anionic dye molecules. However, the introduction of positively charged substituent group $[(CH_3)_3N^+]$ imparts strongly basic anion exchange character and enhances the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent even in alkaline medium. Hence, the synthesised quaternary aminised guar $[(CH_3)_3N^+]$ derivative is able to adsorb the dye at higher pH region also.

Effect of substituents: To study the effect of substituent groups on the adsorption of dyes,

TABLE 3—ADSORPTION CAPACITIES (K) AND INTENSITY OF ADSORPTION 1/n OF DIFFERENT GUAR DERIVATIVES CONTACTED WITH DIRECT RED DYE AT pH 7

Sl. no.	Derivative	Adsorption capacity K × 10 ⁴		Intensity of adsorption 1/n	
		Graphical	Calcd.	Graphical	Calcd.
1.	Cross-linked guar	1.20	1.20	0.50	0.52
2.	Diethylaminohydroxypropyl	1.74	1.73	0.46	0.47
3.	Quaternary aminised [(CH ₃) ₃ N] ⁺	2.19	2.22	0.70	0.67
4.	Quaternary aminised [(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N] ⁺	3.02	3.08	0.88	0.88

the cross-linked guar was also substituted with [(C₂H₅)₃N]⁺ and [(C₂H₅)₂N]⁺ groups. The adsorption behaviour of these derivatives, trimethyl aminised derivative and cross-linked guar were studied with direct red dye at pH 7 under identical experimental conditions. The K and 1/n values obtained from the respective plots are given in Table 3. The value of 1/n is less than unity showing a favourable adsorption for all these derivatives at pH 7. The adsorption capacity was found⁶ to be in the following order.

This is in good agreement with the values of salt splitting capacities of these derivatives (0.62, 0.28, 0.13 and zero meq/g, respectively). The lower adsorption capacity of cross-linked and [(C₂H₅)₂N]⁺-guar derivatives can be attributed to the absence of any positive charge.

Effect of initial dye concentration: The effect of initial dye concentration on the removal efficiency of the adsorbent [(CH₃)₃N]⁺-guar derivative was studied at three different pH (3, 5 and 7) with procion brill orange H₃R and direct red dye at pH 7 only. The values of K (adsorption capacity) and 1/n were calculated from the plots of log X/m vs log C at 100 and 150 ppm concentrations. The results of direct red dye are given in Fig. 2. The values of K as determined by the plots, were found to be higher at initial lower concentrations of the

Fig. 2. Effect of initial dye (direct red) concentration on adsorption: —●—●—●— 100 ppm, —○—○—○— 150 ppm.

dye concerned. This appears to be due to the abundant availability of the adsorbent surface to the dye molecules at lower concentrations.

Studies with textile effluent: The adsorption of colour in the textile effluent by quaternary aminised [(CH₃)₃N]⁺ derivative was studied at different pH. The percentage decrease in O.D., which is a measurement of total dye concentration in the effluent at different pH was plotted against the

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on decrease in O.D. of textile effluent: —○—○—○— pH 3, —●—●—●— 5, —□—□—□— 7, —△—△—△— 10.

Fig. 4. Decrease in O.D. of effluent by different guar gum derivatives at pH 5: —○—○—○— Quaternary aminised [(CH₃)₃N]⁺-guar derivative, —△—△—△— Quaternary aminised [(C₂H₅)₃N]⁺-guar derivative, —●—●—●— Diethylaminohydroxy propyl guar derivatives, —□—□—□— Cross linked guar.

amount of derivative added (Fig. 3). The percentage decrease in O.D. appears to be maximum at lower pH. This is also in accordance with our observation with direct helio B dye (Table 2).

To calculate the minimum amount required to remove maximum colour from the effluent, the percentage removal of O.D. were plotted against the amount of different adsorbents at pH 5, which was selected as the suitable pH (Fig. 4). The figure shows that, at lower concentrations of colour constituents in the effluent, the percentage decrease in O.D. is proportional to the amount of adsorbent added. At higher concentrations the percentage decrease tends to reach a limiting value. Further, higher amounts of adsorbent do not decrease the O.D. of the effluent proportionally.

Conclusion : The findings of this study are

- (i) Guar gum derivatives are fairly good adsorbent for the removal of colour due to their capacity to remove all the classes of anionic dyes and other organic toxic constituents of textile effluent.
- (ii) The percentage removal of colour is dependent on pH, initial dye concentrations and the substituent group on guar.

- (iii) The treatment of textile effluent is simple and treated water can be reused in the textile industry.

These adsorbents being cheap, harmless and biodegradable, eliminate the problems of regeneration and disposal.

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